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MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Dear students,

I would like to congratulate the present committee (2021-22) of the Student's Geographical Association for their hard work and dedication to publish the 56th volume of the "OBSERVER", an annual journal with ISSN No. 2230-9535. With the regular contributions from faculty members, research scholars and students across national and international institutions, this journal has been the symbol of academic pride and excellence of this department since its inception by late Prof. S.P. Chatterjee. The Journal has emerged as a platform to focus on the development of geographical understanding and its implementation towards the real-world geographical problems.

I on behalf of the faculty members, non-teaching staff, Research scholars and students wish the Student's Geographical Association all success and once again congratulate all the contributors of this volume.

Dr. Debasis Ghosh

Associate Professor & Head, Department of Geography

President, The Student's Geographical Association

University of Calcutta

From The Desk of Secretary

The annual journal of the association “The observer”, Volume 56th is published on teacher’s day 5th of September and contains valuable writings of eminent geographers, professors, research scholars and the students of our department.

It would not be out of the place to mention that without the guidance and inspiration of our respected professors and seniors of the Department, the success of the journal would have been impossible.

We express our earnest gratitude to all the teaching and non-teaching staffs, advisors and the students of Geography Department for their cordial cooperation and continuous support.

Pallab Gayen
(General Secretary)

Sudipta Das
Chetana Roy
Simanta Koley
(Assistant General Secretary)

Note from the editors

Esteemed Readers,

It gives us great pleasure and honour to announce that Department of Geography will celebrate teacher's day on 5th of September, 2022 at Ballygunge Science College campus, University of Calcutta by the students' Geographical Association. On this auspicious occasion, we are delighted to publish the 56th volume of our annual journal "THE OBSERVER" (ISSN: 2230-9535).

In this regard, we would like to express our sincere appreciation to our respected professors for their tireless cooperation and helpful recommendations throughout the editing of these articles. They have always served as a source of inspiration for us.

We did our best to choose and publish papers from different dimensions of Geography exploring new horizons. Our goal of this journal is to encourage publication from research scholars, teachers and student of geography. Furthermore, we would like to mention that this journal serves as a common platform for students to encourage their writing skills and publish their research ideas. This journal was created by student for student, and where young and old hands meet in terms of knowledge and ideas. This year, we have tried to deliver you this journal in a much better way, but we humbly apologize for all our inadvertent shortcomings.

The note remains incomplete if we do not acknowledge the encouragement and wholehearted support from our fellow classmates, juniors, scholars, the office staffs and the librarians.

Thanking you,

Yours truly,
Pulak Barman
Saptadipa Ghosal
Soumita Ghosh
(Editors)

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ASSESSMENT OF ROLE OF INTRA-STATE MIGRATION ON URBANISATION IN WEST BENGAL, 1991-2011

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Abstract: *Migration and urbanization have been directly linked since the ancient period but in the 19th century after the Industrial Revolution in Europe migration emerged as a strong factor of urbanisation. Migration refers to the mobility of the individuals or group of individuals from one place to another place for permanent or temporary settlement in the new place. It is one of the most important components of population dynamics. Migration influenced the demography of origin and also destination places. It plays an important role in urbanisation. In the present study I have analysed the migration pattern, stream, trend and the urbanisation process of West Bengal for 1991 to 2011 time period.*

Keywords: *Migration, Urbanisation, West Bengal.*

Introduction

The term migration refers to the mobility of people from one administrative area to another area with intentions of settling permanently or temporarily. In other words, human migration implies the change of residence by an individual or group. Migration is one of the most important key factors of population dynamics. Rural out migration plays an important role in the growth of urban centres; it is also responsible for growth of slum individuals in urban areas. As per United Nation estimation, the rapid urbanisation and migration would lead to tripling of slum population by 2050.

Urbanisation is the process of increasing the number of populations in urban areas (Davis, 1965). It is progressive concentration of population in urban units. Different countries have different criteria to define urban areas. Census of India also has some criteria to defined urban centre which are:

In the **pre-Independence India**, the following criteria was fixed to define the urban in India (Census of India, 1911; also see Bhagat, 2005)

- Every municipality of whatever size.
- All civil lines (not included within municipal limits).
- Permanent habitation with continuous collection of houses of not less than 5,000 persons.

After independence the census of India modified the criteria of urban. Since the 1961 Census, an urban area was determined based on two important criteria i.e., statutory administration and certain economic and demographic indicators. The first criterion includes civic status of towns, and the second refers to the characteristics like population size, density of population, and percentage of the workforce in the non-agricultural sector. In **1961 census** adopted a strict definition to treat all places satisfying the following conditions as towns:

- All municipal corporations, municipal boards, cantonments and notified areas.
- All localities though not in themselves local bodies but forming part of a city or town agglomeration.

- Population exceeds 5,000.
- At least 75 percent of the working population engages in non-agricultural activity.
- The density exceeds 400 persons per square km.

In the **1981 census**, criteria of urban area definition again have been changed. All the criteria were same in addition, instead of 75% overall workforce, 75% male workforce engaged in non-agriculture activities and excluded the workers engaged in livestock, forestry, fishing, hunting and plantation, orchards and allied activities.

In 2001, the census of India modified the criteria of urban area. Instead of 75% male worker, 75% main male worker has been adopted as a criterion of urban definition and others criteria has same.

Since the dawn of human society migration has shaping the human civilization but with the beginning of the industrial revolution in the Europe it emerged as a more intensified forces of shaping the cities and urbanisation and closely linked with the urban transition, influencing the demand and supply of labour, economic growth and human well-being (Bhagat, 2018) (Adam, 2004). In the globalization era, urbanisation and migration are the direct manifestation of the economic development of any country. Understanding the causes and consequences of migration in terms of changes in population and economic activity distribution as well as the success and failure of the state and state and others organization intervention, would be critical for evaluating policy options and exploring areas of possible strategic intervention. In the developing and underdeveloped countries, migration is linked with the stagnation and volatility of agriculture and lack of sectoral diversification within agrarian economies. Agricultural production and continuous decrease of income, lack of job opportunity in rural areas, poor infrastructure has led to out migration from backward rural areas and most of the migrants absorbed by the urban informal economy (Shukla et al., 2010). The present paper is an attempt to analyse the level of urbanisation with the emphasis on migration in West Bengal for the time period of 1991 to 2011.

Theoretical Framework

Industrial revolution, on one side, has led to economic prosperity in the country and creates job opportunities and technological development leads to surplus labour in agricultural activities. When technological development creates the surplus labour in the rural agrarian society in one side and another side industrial development in urban area creates the labour demand as a result wage differential become more intensified between rural and urban area. As per neo classical theory given by Lewis (1954), Todaro and Harris (1970), Ranis and Fei (1961) migration is a result of wage differential and employment conditions between countries (Douglas S. Massey, 1993). Migration is the result of transformation of the traditional agrarian sector (Bhagat, 2018). After the industrial revolution urbanisation process continuously increased in both developed and developing countries. In the beginning of the 20th century only 13 % of the global population was urban and in 1950 it reached 29 %. Finally at the end of the 20th century about 50 % of the population lived in urban areas (Bhagat, 2009). Urbanization changes the place and space and creates agglomeration economies in the favour of increasing productivity and economic growth which leads to labour mobility. Although the relationship between urbanisation, labour mobility and economic development is not straightforward, it is mediated by global and local processes, both spatial and historical. Migration and urbanisation affect both origin and destination. The agglomeration economies, lower cost of production, size of consumer and capital market, cheap labour benefit destination area as well as flow of remittances, return migration benefited the origin area (Bhagat, 2018). In this current paper I have focused on the migration within west Bengal and urbanisation in different districts.

Objectives

- Analyse the trend and level of Urbanisation.
- Pattern of intrastate migration.
- Look at the effect of migration on urbanisation.

Data and Methodology

In the present study I have been used migration, urban population data which taken from census of India. From the primary census abstract, I have taken urban population data for various censuses (1991-2011) and the D series table provides migration related data. In the census 2001 and 2011, D 11 table provide the inter-district in migration and outmigration data but in case of 1991 D 15 table provide that data and Table D 10 data provide the migration stream data of state.

Census of India provides data in the absolute number. Sometimes absolute data is not suitable to make proper sense about intensity of phenomena therefore in this case percentage makes a sound sense. In the present study, absolute data have been transformed into percentages to make sense. To transforming the absolute data into percentage I have used some basic formula which are:

Percentage of Urban Population which is used to expressed the level of urbanisation is

$$\frac{\text{Urban population of the district}}{\text{Total population of the district}} * 100$$

Decadal growth of urban population measured by the following formula

$$\frac{\text{Urban Population of the present year} - \text{urban population of the previous year}}{\text{Urban population of the previous year}} * 100$$

To calculate the percentage of migration stream I have used this formula

$$\frac{\text{Number of migrants who are migrated from rural to urban of the district}}{\text{Total Mirants of the district}} * 100$$

Same formula has been used to calculate other migration streams also but only the numerator changes accordingly.

In case of calculating the percentage of in migration and out migration of the district, the formula has been used as

$$\frac{\text{Number of In Migrants or Out Migrants of the district}}{\text{Total population of the District}} * 100$$

In this present study I have used various cartographic techniques like line graph, Choropleth maps to show different phenomena.

Results

Level of Urbanization

In 1901 India's urban population was 25.8 million constituting 10.8 % of the total population, in 2001 it reached 286.1 million comprising 27.8 % and it had increased to 377.7 million in 2011 constituting 31.16%. In West Bengal the percentage of urban population was 31.87 in 2011 which is slightly above the national level. Table 1 shows the percentage and growth rate of urban population of West Bengal from 1991 to 2011 and fig 1 shows only the percentage of urban population. From the table we can see that the percentage of urban population to total population of West Bengal drastically increased from 2001 to 2011 decade. The percentage of urban population was almost the same between 1991 and 2001. The growth rate has unimaginably increased during 2001 and 2011. Due to New Economic policy (1991) sectoral diversification takes place not only West Bengal throughout the country. Between 2001 and 2011 census in India census town has increased from 5161 to 7933 and only in West Bengal it increased to 493. After the New Economic Policy, the government reduced subsidies in Chemical Fertilizer, irrigation facility, electricity that is why agriculture became non profitable and small and marginal farmers left the agricultural activities and engaged in informal activities. Because of this sectoral diversification the number of census towns increased rapidly (Das, 2015).

Table 1: Percentage and Growth Rate of Urban Population, 1991-2011.

Year	% Of Urban Population	Growth Rate (%)
1991	27.47	-
2001	27.97	19.88
2011	31.87	29.72

Source: Census of India, 1991-2011.

Fig 1: Percentage of Urban Population in West Bengal, 1991-2011.

Emergence of New Census Town

During 2001 and 2011 in India, the number of census towns has increased from 5161 to 7933, a total 2772 new census towns have been added in India's town list and in West Bengal 493 (Das, 2015). This new census town has a crucial effect on the drastic growth of urban population in West Bengal. Table 2 shows the number of census towns identified in West Bengal. Census Town has a major effect on growth of urban population in every district. Because of the sectoral diversification, the number of census towns has increased drastically (Das, 2015). After the New Economic Policy, the government has reduced subsidies in various agricultural sectors like Chemical fertilizer, electricity, irrigation etc. Therefore, production cost has increased and cultivation has become unprofitable. Because of this several marginal and smaller farmers migrated to the urban area and engaged in the non-formal activity. In this way urbanisation has rapidly increased in this period (Mishra, 2020).

Table 2: Number of Census Town in West Bengal.

District	Eligible villages in 2001	Identified New CTs (2011) from the eligible village	Total Identified New CTs in 2011	Total Mismatch
Koch Bihar	8	8	8	0
Uttar Dinajpur	3	3	3	0
Dakshin Dinajpur	6	5	5	1
Maldah	37	23	24	15
Murshidabad	43	39	43	8
Birbhum	13	13	13	0
Bardhaman	33	32	33	2
Nadia	39	39	40	1
North 24 Parganas	58	55	58	6
Hugli	41	37	38	5
Bankura	7	7	7	0
Puruliya	17	16	16	1
Haora	88	82	85	9
South 24 Parganas	94	85	97	21
Paschim Medinipur	9	6	7	4
Purba Medinipur	13	13	16	3
Total	509	463	493	76

Source: (Das, 2015).

District Wise Percentage of Urban Population and Growth Rate

Table 3 shows the district wise percentage of urban population and decadal growth of urban population of different districts of West Bengal from 1991 and 2011. Percentage of urban population in each and every district has increased from 1991 to 2011. Kolkata has the highest percentage of urban population followed by Haora, North 24 Pargana and lowest urban population in Bankura (8.33%) followed by Cooch Behar (10.27%). Growth rate of urban population in west Bengal has increased from 19.88 to 29.72 percent. Highest growth rate found in Malda district (124.81 % decadal growth rate) followed by south 24 pargana (92.21), Murshidabad (91.16) and lowest growth rate found in north 24 pargana. Only Kolkata has found a negative growth rate with – 1.67 %. From fig 2 we find that in Cooch Behar, North 24 Pargana and Kolkata district the urban population growth rate is lower than previous decade. Jalpaiguri, Darjeeling, Malda, Murshidabad, Birbhum, Murshidabad, Birbhum, Nadia, Puruliya, Haora and south 24 pargana have higher growth rate than state growth rate. Fig 3-5 shows the district wise

percentage of urban population from 1991 to 2011. I have categories the entire state in 4 categories which are low up to 15% to total population shown by green colour, moderate 15-35 % shown by yellow, high 35 to 50% light brown and very high shown by red colour urbanised district more than 50% population lived in urban area. Only Kolkata, Haora and North 24 Pargana have fallen under a very high category with more than 50% urban population.

Table 3: Shows the Percentage of Urban Population and Decadal Growth Rate.

State/ District	% Of Urban Population			Growth Rate (%)	
	1991	2001	2011	2001	2011
West Bengal	27.47	27.97	31.87	19.88	29.72
Darjeeling	30.47	32.34	39.42	31.40	39.88
Jalpaiguri	16.36	17.84	27.38	32.44	74.72
Koch Bihar	7.81	9.10	10.27	33.11	28.28
Uttar Dinajpur	-	12.06	12.05	-	23.02
Dakshin Dinajpur	-	13.10	14.10	-	20.04
Maldah	7.07	7.32	13.58	29.16	124.81
Murshidabad	10.43	12.49	19.72	48.22	91.16
Birbhum	8.98	8.57	12.83	12.57	73.92
Bardhaman	35.09	36.94	39.89	19.97	20.86
Nadia	22.63	21.27	27.84	12.35	46.90
North 24 Parganas	51.23	54.30	57.27	30.04	18.17
Hugli	31.19	33.47	38.57	24.26	26.11
Bankura	8.29	7.37	8.33	1.19	27.43
Puruliya	9.44	10.07	12.74	21.63	46.15
Haora	49.58	50.36	63.38	16.38	42.85
Kolkata	100	100.00	100.00	3.93	-1.67
South 24 Parganas	13.3	15.73	25.58	42.85	92.21
Paschim Medinipur	-	-	12.22	19.84	-
Purba Medinipur	9.85	10.23	11.63	-	-

Sources: Census of India (1991-2011).

Fig: 2 Growth Rate of Urban Population in Different districts of West Bengal, 1991-2011

Fig 3: Percentage of urban population in 1991.

Fig 4: % of urban population in 2001.

Fig 5: % of urban population in 2011.

District Wise Inter District Migration

Inter district migration refers to movement of people from one district to another district. In the present study migration is measured on the basis of place of birth and place of enumeration data. If the district of birth and district of enumeration is different, it is considered as migration. Table 4 shows the inter-district in migration, out migration and net migration from 1991 to 2011 of different districts of West Bengal. Net migration measured by subtracting total out migration of a district from the total in migration of that district. If the net migration value shows in negative then it indicates the out migration is more than in migration and that district might be losing its population. Fig 6 shows the in migration, fig 7 shows the out migration and fig 8 shows the net migration of all districts of West Bengal from 1991 to 2011. The percentage of in migration, out migration has increased in this time period in all the districts. When we focused on net migration we can find Cooch Behar, Dakshin Dinajpur, Murshidabad, Birbhum, Bardhaman, Nadia, Bankura, Kolkata, Purba and Paschim Medinipur has negative net migration which indicates from these more out-migrate than in migration to another district. Kolkata has the highest negative net migration (-21.02%) followed by Koch Bihar (-2.94), Nadia (-2.48). From this table we can get only the volume of migration but what is the impact of migration on urbanisation could not be understood. For this we have to discuss the migration stream mainly rural to urban and urban to rural migration.

Table 4: Percentage of In-Migration, Out-Migration and Net Migration (1991-2011).

District	% Of In Migration			% Of Out Migration			% Of Net Migration		
	1991	2001	2011	1991	2001	2011	1991	2001	2011
<i>Darjeeling</i>	2.15	4.51	5.79	1.36	3.86	4.78	0.80	0.65	1.01
<i>Jalpaiguri</i>	1.34	5.07	6.15	0.84	2.74	3.81	0.50	2.33	2.34
<i>Koch Bihar</i>	0.50	2.25	3.21	1.19	4.96	6.15	-0.69	-2.70	-2.94
<i>Uttar Dinajpur</i>	-	4.21	4.13	-	2.41	2.75	-	1.80	1.39
<i>Dakshin Dinajpur</i>	-	3.37	4.29	-	3.95	5.26	-	-0.58	-0.97
<i>Maldah</i>	0.60	1.97	2.14	1.15	3.16	3.38	-0.55	-1.19	-1.24
<i>Murshidabad</i>	0.57	2.65	3.17	1.47	4.56	4.75	-0.89	-1.91	-1.57
<i>Birbhum</i>	1.16	5.08	5.80	1.50	5.87	6.77	-0.34	-0.79	-0.97
<i>Bardhaman</i>	2.40	7.31	8.43	1.25	5.96	9.60	1.16	1.35	-1.17
<i>Nadia</i>	1.32	5.19	6.90	1.84	7.14	9.38	-0.52	-1.95	-2.48
<i>North 24 Parganas</i>	1.70	10.05	13.49	0.90	2.89	3.65	0.80	7.16	9.84
<i>Hugli</i>	1.73	9.37	11.05	1.21	6.39	8.18	0.52	2.97	2.87
<i>Bankura</i>	0.78	5.34	6.13	2.22	7.99	8.59	-1.44	-2.65	-2.46
<i>Puruliya</i>	0.71	2.73	8.66	1.15	4.17	3.86	-0.43	-1.44	4.80
<i>Haora</i>	1.35	6.29	6.94	1.34	5.64	6.42	0.01	0.65	0.51
<i>Kolkata</i>	2.23	6.12	6.53	2.32	17.50	27.55	-0.09	-	-
								11.38	21.02
<i>South 24 Parganas</i>	1.25	4.05	5.66	0.86	3.37	3.69	0.40	0.68	1.97
<i>Paschim Medinipur</i>	-	-	4.45	-	-	5.67	-	-	-1.23
<i>Purba Medinipur</i>	-	-	3.60	-	-	3.63	-	-	-0.03

Source: Census of India, 1991, 2001 & 2011.

Fig 6: Percentage of In-Migration in Different Districts of West Bengal, 1991-2011.

Fig 7: Percentage of Out Migration in Different Districts of West Bengal, 1991-2011.

Fig 8: Percentage of Net Migration in Different District of West Bengal, 1991-2011.

Pattern of migration

As we know internal migration can be categorized into different migration streams which are rural to rural, rural to urban, urban to rural and urban to urban. These four migration streams are too important to analyse the urbanization process. Among four streams, the rural-to-rural migration stream has no effect on urbanization but urban to urban has little effect on urbanisation because this migration stream could grow an urban centre of destination. But rural to urban and urban to rural migration streams have more impact on urbanisation. Rural to rural stream adds population to an urban area and urban to rural migration stream reduces the urban population; and net balance of these two streams is the actual contribution to the process of urbanisation (Bhagat, 2009). Table 5 shows the stream of migration of West Bengal according to migration streams. In 2011 rural to rural migration stream constituted 61.96 % of the total intra state migration which reduced to 51.50 % in 2001. Rural to urban migration constituted 6.16% in 2001 and 8.33 % in 2011, the amount of rural to urban migration has increased. Urban to rural migration constituted 15.52 % in 2001 and increased to 17.26 % of all migration streams and urban to urban migration constituted 12.60% in 2001 and it also increased 17.82

% in 2011. The growth rate of intra state migration in West Bengal is 28.07 %. Among all streams, the growth rate is high in Urban-to-Urban migration (81.13%) followed by rural to urban migration (73.04%). In the present study I only focused on intra state migration and urbanisation process. In case of in-state migration I find that females are dominated because of marriage and consequent parental residence change and move to husband's residence (Bhagat, 2009). This is evident by the sex ratio which is presented in the table 4. Here the sex ration is show males per 1000 female. If we look on the sex ratio, we find that sex ratio is very low for all the migration streams.

Net Balance of Migration Stream

Earlier I have discussed the migration streams. Among the four types of migration streams only rural to urban and urban to rural migration have an impact on urbanisation process (Bhagat, 2009). The net balance of these two migrations streams has an actual contribution to the urbanisation process. The net balance of the migration stream has been measured by subtracting urban to rural migration from rural to urban, this indicates the number of migrants added or lost from urban areas of an area. Negative net balance refers to loss of population from the urban area through migration and positive net balance refers to ads of population in urban areas and as a result urbanisation happened. Table 6 shows the net balance of the migration stream and fig 9 is the graphical representation of this data table. From this data table I have found that Cooch Behar, Nadia, Bankura and Paschim Medinipur have positive net balance of migration stream but it is very low and negligible for urbanisation. The rest of all districts have a negative net balance of migration stream.

Table 5: Migration Stream of West Bengal, 2001-2011

Area Name	Place of Enumeration	Place of Last Resident	Person		Percentage of Migration Stream		Growth Rate (2001-2011)	Sex Ratio	
			2001	2011	2001	2011		2001	2011
West Bengal	Rural	Rural	4322170	4600851	61.96	51.5	6.45	214	171
West Bengal	Rural	Urban	429853	743803	6.16	8.33	73.04	664	631
West Bengal	Urban	Rural	1082583	1541451	15.52	17.2	42.39	820	587
West Bengal	Urban	Urban	878721	1591612	12.60	17.8	81.13	744	705
		Total Migration	6975224	8933321			28.07		

Source: Census of India, 2001 & 2011

Table 6: Net Balance of the Migration Stream, 2001-2011.

State/District	2001		2011	
	Person	Percentage of migrants	Person	Percentage of Migrants
West Bengal	-652730	-9.36	-797648	-8.93
Darjeeling	-7742	-7.81	-24411	-12.99
Jalpaiguri	-6921	-2.24	-43822	-11.35
Koch Bihar	1264	0.67	2368	1.02
Uttar Dinajpur	-9929	-5.14	-25260	-10.73
Dakshin Dinajpur	803	0.55	-2056	-1.49
Malda	-326	-0.11	-23726	-7.70
Murshidabad	-21935	-5.52	-38453	-6.32
Birbhum	-704	-0.25	-2105	-0.64
Bardhaman	-99948	-15.89	-67127	-8.15
Nadia	-14427	-3.25	80	0.01

North 24 Parganas	-177244	-18.81	-201893	-15.06
Hugli	-55021	-9.65	-66468	-9.75
Bankura	23022	7.14	40855	10.95
Puruliya	-7018	-3.67	-5108	-2.25
Haora	-85135	-22.66	-139670	-27.85
Kolkata	-128795	-63.19	-99613	-50.16
South 24 Parganas	-32281	-5.94	-75191	-9.08
Paschim Medinipur	-	-	5101	1.03
Purba Medinipur	-	-	-31149	-6.71

Source: Census of India, 2001 & 2011.

Fig 9: Net Balance of Migration Stream, 2001-2011

Conclusion

From the above discussion I find that there is little impact of intra state migration in urbanization. When I have analysed the migration stream, I find that urban to urban migration stream has the highest percentage of total migration, followed by rural to urban migration. Net balance of the migration stream which has an important effect on urbanization shows negative value for almost all the districts. Which indicates intra state migration has no effect on urbanization. Among all the migration streams are dominated by female migration, the main reason is marriage. And it is evident from the sex ratio of the migration stream. But in every district the percentage of urban population has increased during the 1991 to 2011 time period. The main reason for the increasing percentage of urban population in every district of West Bengal is the increased number of new Census towns during this time period. In West Bengal 493 Census towns have increased in the 2011 census. It has a major effect on the urban population growth in West Bengal. Due to sectoral diversification means people have shifted their livelihood from agricultural activity to non-agricultural activities, the number of census towns has increased. From this study we could conclude that intra state migration has less effect on urbanisation. The emergence of new census towns has more to increasing urbanisation.

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